

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL DESCRIPTION OF THE CLINICAL EXPRESSION OF CHRONIC CHOLECYSTITIS IN THE GERONT-SUPERGERONT POPULATION OF THE FERGANA VALLEY BY SEVERITY LEVEL

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Relevance and necessity of the topic.

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Cholecystitis as a therapeutic, surgical problem and as an almost untapped topical issue in the "field of preventive medicine", especially in the geront and supergeront population, remains until now. According to UNESCO data, hermatric groups of earthlings are considered to be the fastest growing layer [3; 5]. It is clear from this that cholecystitis is the number one problem in the geront and supergeront population and remains the most urgent topic not only in surgical gastroenterology, but also in preventive medicine.

The aim of the research: It consists of studying and determining the epidemiological, clinical and prophylactic features of cholecystitis in the young, middle-aged, geront and supergeront population of different regions of Uzbekistan.

Materials and research methods. This research is considered a simultaneous epidemiological investigation and it is based on the analysis of the results obtained in a population of 2682 people. Residents of 6 regions of the country - Andijan, Namangan, Fergana, Jizzakh, Syrdarya and Kashkadarya - were involved in the research. Based on the tasks set in the work, 6 simultaneous epidemiological studies were organized and carried out in the valley and oasis regions of Uzbekistan.

A detailed description of the organization and conduct of the epidemiological research was provided: the screening group was formed, questionnaires were prepared, and the screening group was introduced to the necessary equipment for the research. A procedure for working with the population was created and a procedure for checking the population was developed.

Results and Discussions. The frequency of detection of chronic cholecystitis in the geront and supergeront population of Fergana Valley was studied according to severity. The obtained results show that the mild course of chronic cholecystitis in the geront-supergeront population of the Valley (n=82/4) is 60.2% (non-stone and stone types - 57.9% and 2.3%) and 100.0%

(stone-free and stone types – from 100.0% and 0.00%) is confirmed in detection frequencies (RR=1.878; 95% CI=0.704 – 5.012; $\chi^2=9.832$; S=0.320; P <0.05)

Moderate severity of chronic cholecystitis (n=41/1) is diagnosed in geront population - 30.8% (stoneless type - 25.6% and stone type - 5.3%) and 0.00%.

The severity of the disease (n=12/0) is determined in the frequency of 9.0% (non-stone type - 1.5% and stone type - 7.5%) in geronts in valley conditions; not recorded in supergeronts.

The conclusions of the same analysis on Oasis are confirmed as follows: 1) chronic cholecystitis is mild (n=21/0) in the geront population of Oasis - 48.8%. Its non-stone type is 48.8% and its stone type is determined from 0.00%. Not recorded in supergeront population; 2) moderate severity of chronic cholecystitis (n=14/0) is not recorded in the supergeront population, and in the geront population it is confirmed at a frequency of 32.6% (27.9% of non-stone type and 4.7% of stone type); 3) severe course of chronic cholecystitis (n=8/0) in the geront population, under the conditions of Oasis, is noted with a frequency of 18.6%, non-stone and stone types - 2.3% and 16.3%, respectively. Not recorded in supergeronts.

Epidemiological descriptions of the occurrence of chronic cholecystitis in the geront and supergeront population of the territory of Uzbekistan by severity level confirmed that the mild course of chronic cholecystitis in the geront and supergeront population of the territory of Uzbekistan (n=103/4) in the geront population - 57.4% (Chronic cholecystitis without stones - 55.7% and Chronic cholecystitis with stones - 1.7%) and 100.0% (Chronic cholecystitis without stones - 100.0% and Chronic cholecystitis with stones - 0.00%) are detected (RR=1.961; 95% CI=0.736) – 5.227; $\chi^2=24.713$; P<0.001).

The average course of the disease (n=55/1) is characterized by the distribution frequency of 31.3% in the geront population, and non-stone and stone types are observed in 26.1% and 5.1% frequencies. Not recorded in supergeronts.

Severe clinical course of chronic cholecystitis (n=20/0) is confirmed in the geront population with a frequency of 11.4% (non-stone type - 1.7% and stone type - 9.7%), not recorded in supergeronts.

Conclusion. It can be concluded that in the geront age (≥ 90 years old) population, chronic cholecystitis has a prognostic significance, with a severe course of up to 11.4% and a mild course of up to 57.4%; These results serve to conduct differentiated early treatment-preventive measures.

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